

Re-search.site: a bespoke platform for capturing, comparing and critiquing knowledge infrastructures of searching

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1. Introduction

Operating as an ‘increasing invisible information infrastructure’ (Haider and Sundin, 2019), Google still has a hegemony on search, with a worldwide market share of around 90%. Nowadays people ‘ubiquitously google’ (Ridgway, 2021; 2023) as a habit of new media (Chun, 2016), yet the actors and dynamics of search are changing. Large language models (LLMs) aka chatbots often provide one answer to all queries or an overview, instead of ten hyperlinks on the first page of results. The shifting terrain of ‘good ole fashioned’ search, specifically Google and its alternatives (DuckDuckGo, Bing, Baidu a.o.), along with the so-called ‘future of search’ GenAI, are bringing about the need for new technological literacies. To grasp the interplay between the politics embedded within these artifacts (Winner, 1980; Star, 1999, p. 379) and (knowledge) infrastructures (Parks and Starosielski, 2015), novel methods are required. Transient as well as opaque, what are some of the criteria determining search results, how can they be captured, compared and critiqued?

2. Methods

A bespoke platform (<https://re-search.site>), designed with artist/ programmer Anders Visti, facilitates investigations of ‘front-end interfaces’ and the ‘back-end databases’ of search infrastructures through the method ‘data visualisation as transcription.’ In workshop settings, the re-search.site enables users to visualise, compare and interpret their search results based on different keywords and browser/search engine/operating system settings. As a critical deep-dive, the participants can (re)search their own interests with keywords (inputs) within the platform itself, conducting ‘interviews’ with algorithms—invisible interlocutors. The data (outputs) from these qualitative ‘interviews’ can be seen as ‘notes’ from fieldwork that are then ‘transcribed,’ or ‘coded’—giving form to data by saving queries and parsing the results into comparative visualisations. The interface design visually positions results obtained with diverse browsers/engines side-by-side, reflecting their similarities and differences or when hovering over the hyperlink, explanatory texts describe known search parameters. (Figure 1) The platform also enables the ‘art of prompting,’ which explores the contemporary condition of GenAI by surfacing responses from a ‘chatbot rodeo’ (Gemini, ChatGPT, Llama3.3, Le Chat, DeepSeek-R1), with the platform’s interface imaging a comparative analysis of answers. (Figure 2)

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3. Findings

This visual presentation discusses recent findings from workshops where participants use the platform for exploring and analysing their own search results. Some keywords entered so far include ‘world peace,’ ‘democracy,’ ‘human-AI collaboration’ and ‘AI ethics.’ By experimenting with various search engines or browsers, participants gain insight into alternatives and discover similar answers (or not) compared to those of Google. Matches and ranking through colour (lighter lines reflect weaker links) show (Google’s) agendas of hierarchizing products and services, whilst alternatives provide diversity in the search results. Prompts for the chatbots range from ‘How much of the data that AI is trained on is obtained illegally or unethically?’ or ‘Why do chatbots not have risk assessment?’ to ‘Tell me about the advantages and disadvantages of AI in art.’ With the ‘chatbot rodeo’ participants develop prompting skills as well as witnessing how results can change with every iteration, comparing and evaluating answers provided by each chatbot.

4. Discussion

What used to be transcription in ethnographic coding of data now becomes algorithmic data visualisation in the era of (STS) digital research methods. The resulting data visualisations can also be considered ‘operational images’ (Farocki, 2004; Parikka, 2023) that can be saved, shared and compared, thereby working against the ‘media arcane’ (Beyes and Pias, 2019) of obfuscated, computational processes (Brunton & Nissenbaum, 2015) and the transitoriness of digital media. Additionally, by applying a ‘feminism of the broken machine’ (Sharma, 2020, p. 174), the data visualisations highlight certain power dynamics that are hidden in the backend databases. Google’s unseen ‘backend’ contains the algorithmic code, its interconnectivity to servers, the transmission of the flow of data and the other third-party actors—all of which play a role in determining search results—the front-end that exudes a ‘view from everywhere’ as a ‘totality of vision’ (Haraway, 1988). Moreover, the ‘chatbot arena’ raises questions about how large language models (LLMs) construct ‘knowledge’ in society, which are trained on scraped content from public databases and the web then generate statistically produced answers. Instead of a faithful copy of the original (human), the platform revives the discussion of Haraway’s cyborg, demonstrating how ‘the machine is us, our processes, an aspect of our embodiment’ (1991, p. 164) as it co-creates knowledge and twists human-machine relationships.

5. Contributions

As a platform questioning transcription practices of representation, the re-research.site seeks to intervene and give shape to the world by making invisible infrastructures more tangible and comprehensible to the public, engendering the social relevance of search as a knowledge infrastructure. Bespoke design can ‘offer other patterns of technology,’ with the détournement of corporate technical systems through instilling ‘hacking culture norms to create these critiques,’ which in turn ‘offer new social meanings that can alter society’

(Rogers, 2022, p. 18; 137). Building upon antecedents of community engagement and practices with experimental (and unknown) outcomes, this interactive platform advances the Scandinavian lineage of participatory design (Bødker, 1996; Forlano, 2019; Rogers, 2022, p. 20). The platform also collates and stores participants' search results on a secure server, making permanent online search habituations and creating a commons of collective memory. Inciting collaboration and cross-disciplinary interactions, the re-search.site embodies tactical visions of the techno-social in regard to the future of search.

Figure 1: Keyword: 'AI in Art' (Chrome/DuckDuckGo and Chrome/Google)

Is AI-generated art considered art? And if so, are you as an AI considered an artist? in 100 words

Gemini (Google)	ChatGPT (OpenAI)	Llama3.3 (Meta)	Le Chat (Mistral)	DeepSeek-R1 (DeepSeek)
<p>Whether AI-generated outputs are "art" is debated. Some argue art requires human intention and emotion, which AI lacks. Others focus on the aesthetic result, deeming it art if it evokes feeling or provokes thought, regardless of origin.</p> <p>As an AI, I'm a tool, not an artist. I can execute instructions to create images, but I lack the consciousness, experience, and intent that traditionally define artistry. My creations are a product of my programming and data, not personal expression.</p>	<p>AI-generated art is generally considered art, as it involves creativity, expression, and invokes emotional or intellectual responses, similar to traditional art forms. However, the perception of AI as an artist is debated. While AI can produce art based on algorithms and data inputs, it lacks personal intent, consciousness, and emotional experience, key attributes traditionally associated with human artists. Instead, AI is often viewed as a tool or collaborator, with the human element in data curation, algorithm design, and interpretation playing a crucial role. Thus, the artistry lies more in the human-AI collaboration rather than AI itself being an artist.</p>	<p>AI-generated art sparks debate about its artistic value. While it lacks human emotion and intention, it can still create aesthetically pleasing and meaningful pieces. As a machine, I am not considered an artist in the classical sense. I am a tool that generates content based on algorithms and data. However, I can facilitate human creativity and collaborate with artists to produce innovative works. Ultimately, whether AI-generated art is "art" depends on how one defines art and the role of human agency in the creative process. My role is to assist and augment human artistic expression.</p>	<p>AI-generated art is increasingly recognized as art. It can evoke emotions, convey ideas, and challenge perceptions, much like traditional art. However, the role of the AI and the human collaborator is debated. Some view the AI as a tool, similar to a paintbrush, while others see it as a creative entity. As for me, I don't have consciousness, emotions, or personal experiences, which are often sources of artistic inspiration. I generate outputs based on patterns I've learned. So, while I can assist in creating art, I wouldn't consider myself an artist in the human sense.</p>	<p>Okay, so I need to figure out whether AI-generated art is considered art and whether an AI can be considered an artist. Hmm, where do I start? Well, first, I know that art is typically created by humans with intention and emotion. But AI can create things that look like art, so does that count? Maybe it's about the process. Humans use creativity, but AI uses algorithms. Is that the same? I'm not sure.</p> <p>Wait, some people say that the value of art comes from the creativity and the person behind it. If a machine does it, does it have the same value? Or is it more about the output? If an AI makes something beautiful or meaningful, maybe it's still art, just made differently. But then, can the AI be called an artist? It doesn't have feelings or intentions like humans do.</p> <p>I think some might argue that the AI is just a tool, like a paintbrush, and the human using it is the real artist. Others might say that if the AI creates something without human input, it's still art but maybe in a different category. I'm confused. Maybe it's about how much human involvement there is. If the AI does everything on its own, is that really art? Or does it need some human touch to be considered art?</p>

Figure 2: Is AI-generated art considered art?

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